

Interreg

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Alpine Space

Forest EcoValue

INTERMEDIATE AND FINAL PUBLIC EVENTS IN EACH LL

D.2.1.2

RESPONSIBLE PARTNER: FINPIE/PP1

Interreg Alpine Space Programme 21-27

Carbon neutral and resource sensitive Alpine region

SO 2.2: Promoting the transition to a circular and resource efficient economy

Forest EcoValue:

**Supporting multiple forest ecosystem services through new circular/green/bio
markets and value chains**

Project ID: ASP0100005

List of the Forest EcoValue project partners

- PP1. Finpiemonte SpA – Regional financial and development agency / **Coordinator** [FINPIE]
- PP2. Lombardy Foundation for the Environment – Fondazione Lombardia per l’Ambiente [FLA]
- PP4. National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment – Institut National de Recherche pour l’Agriculture, l’Alimentation et l’Environnement [INRAE]
- PP5. Slovenia Forest Service – Zavod za Gozdove Slovenije [ZGS]
- PP6. Institute for Environmental Planning and Spatial Development GmbH & Co. KG – Institut für Umweltplanung und Raumentwicklung GmbH & Co. KG [Ifuplan]
- PP7. Lombardy Green Chemistry Association – Cluster Lombardo della Chimica Verde [LGCA]
- PP8. University of Graz, Institute of Environmental Systems Sciences [UNIGRAZ]
- PP9. Regional Centre for Forest Property Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes – Centre Régional de la Propriété Forestière [CNPF]
- PP10. The French National Forest Office – Office National des Forêts [ONF]
- PP11. Hozcluster Steiermark – Woodcluster Styria [HCS]

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Glossary

- **LL** Living Lab
- **WP** Work Package
- **FES** Forest Ecosystem Services
- **ES** Ecosystem Services
- **CB** Capacity Building
- **PP** Project Partner
- **FINPIE** Finpiemonte SpA – Regional financial and development agency
- **FLA** Fondazione Lombardia per l'Ambiente
- **INRAE** Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement
- **ZGS** Zavod za Gozdove Slovenije – Slovenia Forest Service
- **Ifuplan** Institut für Umweltplanung und Raumentwicklung GmbH & Co. KG
- **LGCA** Lombardy Green Chemistry Association – Cluster Lombardo della Chimica Verde
- **UNIGRAZ** University of Graz – Institute of Environmental Systems Sciences
- **CNPF** Centre Régional de la Propriété Forestière – Regional Centre for Forest Property Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes
- **ONF** Office National des Forêts
- **HCS** Holzcluster Steiermark – Woodcluster Styria
- **ASFO** Forest Owners' Association
- **CSR** Complemento di Sviluppo Rurale (Regional Rural Development Complement)
- **PSR** Programma di Sviluppo Rurale (Rural Development Programme)
- **GAL** Local Action Group
- **SFS** Slovenia Forest Service
- **SiDG** Slovenski Državni Gozdovi – Slovenian State Forests
- **BSC Kranj** Regional Development Agency of Gorenjska
- **DRAAF** Direction Régionale de l'Alimentation, de l'Agriculture et de la Forêt
- **COFOR** Association des Communes Forestières
- **SME** Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
- **NGO** Non-Governmental Organisation
- **EEIG** European Economic Interest Grouping

- **PNRMB** Parc Naturel Régional du Massif des Bauges
- **CEN74** Conservatoire d’Espaces Naturels de Haute-Savoie
- **ANCT** Agence Nationale de la Cohésion des Territoires
- **FSC** Forest Stewardship Council
- **LWF** Bayerisches Landesamt für Wald und Forstwirtschaft (Bavarian State Institute for Forestry and Forest Management)
- **WBV** Waldbesitzervereinigung (Forest Owners Association, Germany)
- **ERDF** European Regional Development Fund
- **FEADER** Fonds Européen Agricole pour le Développement Rural (European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development)
- **IFESE** Évaluation Française des Écosystèmes et des Services Écosystémiques
- **ICHN** Indemnité Compensatoire de Handicap Naturel
- **FEV** Forest EcoValue
- **NBFC** National Biodiversity Future Centre

1. Introduction

Deliverable D.2.1.2 is part of the WP2 – *Testing an economic approach for managing Forest Ecosystem Services (FES) in a network of Living Labs (LLs)* – and documents the **intermediate and final public events** held in each of the five national Living Labs (Austria, France, Germany, Italy, Slovenia).

These events represent a key moment in the participatory process and are embedded in the project’s co-creation methodology. The intermediate events function as **moments of validation and feedback**, while final events serve as **synthesis and dissemination points**, showcasing results and discussing lessons learned. These public events are distinct from the capacity building (CB) workshops (D.3.2.1) foreseen under WP3, since they serve different purposes:

- LL public events (D.2.1.2) are embedded within the pilot implementation. They take place in each LL territory and involve local and regional actors, focusing on the real-time testing and validation of tools, methodologies, and business models developed in WP1. These events are participatory and action-oriented, often using co-design or open dialogue formats.
- In contrast, the capacity building workshops (D.3.2.1) are transversal training activities, aiming to enhance stakeholders’ general skills and knowledge on FES markets, governance models, and transnational tools developed during the project. They are focused more on knowledge transfer and capacity reinforcement and involve stakeholders beyond the LLs.

In fact, to ensure a clear and well-targeted distinction between the public events held within the Living Labs and the Capacity Building Workshops, project partners engaged in a dedicated discussion for transnational coordination to clarify the different objectives, audiences, and formats of the two types of events.

D.2.1.2. Intermediate and final public events

Target audience: Local/regional target groups in LLs

Purpose: provide updates to the local community and maintain transparency in order to foster the engagement of local target groups.

- ➔ **Intermediate event** keep local stakeholders informed to encourage the continued collaboration.
- ➔ **Final event** offer a comprehensive restitution of the results achieved and the long-term potential of the proposed solutions.

D3.2.1 Regional Capacity Building Workshops

Target audience: from LL territories to the wider region. Forest owners, businesses, public administrations, others.

Purpose: to promote the transferability of the project solutions and methodologies.

- ➔ **Build knowledge** for the adoption of the project solutions and methodologies
- ➔ **Focus on the ecological and economical aspects** to explain how they are addressed in the project

To complete this deliverable, project partners were asked to gather specific information related to each LL public event, including:

- Event agenda
- Number of participants
- Photos or screenshots (if held online)
- Target groups reached
- Press releases
- Media coverage (if available)

This deliverable therefore provides:

- A comprehensive overview of all intermediate and final public events held within the LLs (including title, date, venue, and format);
- A synthesis of the event objectives, key topics discussed, and types and numbers of stakeholders involved;
- A collection of supporting materials to illustrate and document event implementation.

2. Project overview

Forests of the Alpine Space play a key role in climate change mitigation and resilience, providing multiple ecosystem services (ES) and environmental and social benefits such as CO₂ absorption, air pollution reduction, biodiversity enhancement, and protection against natural hazards. However, they are threatened by abandonment, climate change, and territorial degradation, which progressively reduce natural resources and the provision of forest ES (FES). Maintenance costs of Alpine forests are high, and public funds and traditional wood value chains are insufficient to cover them. Economic valuation and payment schemes for FES are widely discussed but rarely successfully applied.

The Forest EcoValue project addresses this challenge by developing innovative, sustainable business models for forest management and maintenance, supporting new bio-based value chains and ES markets, and involving different sectors, public and private actors, and citizens. Restoring and maintaining healthy forests has been recognised as a source of value for the Alpine region, while also creating business opportunities and green jobs for Alpine communities.

The project focuses on a subset of FES from the following categories:

- **Provisioning** (e.g. biomass, raw materials, chemicals) with a specific focus on non-timber forest products, and on the production of woody biomass for energy, integrated into circular energy markets.
- **Regulating** (e.g. biodiversity, natural risk reduction, CO₂ absorption) concretely working on carbon and biodiversity credits, natural risk management through protective forests, and innovative environmental finance instruments such as green bonds and reverse auctions.
- **Cultural** (e.g. recreation, habitat experience, health) particularly enhancing recreational and tourism services and spiritual and cultural services.

These services have been explored and tested within Living Labs (LLs) across five countries, located in different Alpine territories and representing diverse ecological and socio-economic contexts:

- **Italy – Valle Tanaro, Piedmont:** The LL in Valle Tanaro explores innovative approaches to valorising chestnut groves, promoting non-timber forest products, developing carbon and biodiversity credits, and fostering experiential activities linked to forest and rural heritage.
- **France - Haute-Savoie:** Grand Annecy and Thonon LLs focus respectively on two aspects 1) recreational ecosystem services, enhancing the value of forests through the sale of experiences such as ecotourism, outdoor activities, and educational programmes 2) enhancing the value of water regulation services through a public-private partnership.
- **Slovenia – Karavanke Mountains, municipality Tržič:** The Slovenian LL addresses natural risk management with a focus on torrent control, advances solutions for wood biomass supply chains and promotes sustainable tourism and recreational use of forests.
- **Austria – Province of Styria:** The Styrian LL concentrates on biodiversity and habitat provision and carbon sequestration and storage through innovative financing mechanisms such as reverse auctions.
- **Germany – Tegernsee Valley, Upper Bavaria:** The German LL explores spiritual and cultural services, such as forest cemeteries with biodegradable urns, while also fostering habitat and biodiversity conservation through collaborative public-private partnerships.

Accordingly, the project is aiming to:

- Map and analyse the Alpine Space forests delivery capacity of FES;
- Identify and estimate the economic potential, define business models and FES market frameworks;
- Test the models/tools developed by the consortium in pilot LLs involving local players;
- Compare results at transnational level, identifying obstacles and facilitating factors;
- Analyse the need for innovative policies to foster forest maintenance, FES markets, and new value chains;
- Elaborate refined transferable tools/models and policy proposals to enable new markets and value chains and ensure the expected FES.

Throughout the project, a continuous participatory process is carried out within the Living Labs. Stakeholders' active involvement in these labs is essential for co-designing and testing models and tools, ensuring that the innovative approaches are rooted in local realities. In parallel, public events and capacity-building workshops have strengthened engagement, supported knowledge transfer, and provided regular updates on project activities. This participatory and long-term approach, tested across the five territories, is paving the way for refined, transferable tools and policy proposals that can unlock new markets and value chains while safeguarding the provision of ecosystem services in the Alpine Space.

Project duration: 42 months

3. Summary table of all LL Events

LL Country	Project partner	Event type	Date	Format	TGs reached	Key topics
Austria	PP11, PP8	Intermediate	17.02.2025	Online	TG11, TG16	Participation in Austrian LL
Austria	PP11, PP8	Final	08.10.2025	in person	TG3, TG4, TG5, TG6, TG10, TG11, TG15, TG16, TG17	Results of the Austrian LL and future prospects
France	PP9, PP10	Intermediate	22.05.2024	In person	TG5, TG10, TG11	Water regulation services, Moise watershed model, forest-water management
France	PP9, PP10	Final	29.09.2025	In person	TG1, TG2, TG3, TG4, TG5, TG8, TG9, TG10, TG11, TG12-14 TG16, TG17, TG18, TG19	FES valuation, policy integration, financing mechanisms, public awareness
Germany	PP6	Intermediate	26.09.2025	Online	TG1, TG2, TG12-14, TG16	FES valuation, business models, owner incentives
Germany	PP6	Final	29.09.2025-01.10.2025	In person	TG1-2, TG3-4, TG5, TG11, TG16, TG17	FES quantification, business models, transnational comparison
Italy	PP1	Intermediate	05.09.2025	In person	TG3-4, TG5, TG8-9, TG12-14, TG13	Business model and roadmap validation,

					TG 17	carbon & biodiversity credits, regional alignment
Italy	PP1	Final	27.11.2025	Online	TG3-4, TG5, TG6-7, TG8-9, TG10, TG11, TG12-14, TG17	Synthesis of LL results, policy uptake, cross-LL lessons, scaling opportunities
Slovenia	PP5	Intermediate	28.05.2025	In person	TG1-2, TG5, TG8-9, TG12-14, TG16	Recreation and tourism in forest areas, local engagement
Slovenia	PP5	Final	26.11.2025	In person	TG1-2, TG5, TG6-7, TG8-9, TG10, TG12-14, TG16, TG17	Presentation of LL results and future implementation

4. Individual LL event reports (one section per country)

4.1 Austrian Living Lab – Intermediate event

4.1.1 Event Details

Title: Austrian Living Lab: Reverse actions for protection of biodiversity and stabilizing carbon cycle in Styrian forests (Österreichische Living Lab: Reverse-Auctions für den Schutz der biologischen Vielfalt und Erhöhung der Kohlenstoffstabilität in den steirischen Wäldern)

Date: February 17, 2025, 19:00-20:00

Format: online, using the platform of Forest Monday (Waldmontag), a weekly event hosted by Styrian Forest Owners Association

Agenda:

1. The Importance of Biodiversity and CO₂ Stability (Tobias Stern, University of Graz) 19:00-19:10
2. Project Presentation: Forest EcoValue and the Reverse Auction (Tobias Stern, University of Graz) 19:10-19:30
3. Practical Examples from the Perspective of a Small Forest Owner (Alexander Pinter, WoodCluster Styria and Bernd Poinsett, CEO of Styrian Forest Owners Association) 19:30-19:45
4. Questions and discussion 19:45-20:00

Stakeholders involved:

- Private forest owners (TG16)

- Styrian Forest Owners Association (TG11)

In total, approximately 120 people attended the event.

4.1.2 Content Summary

1. The Importance of Biodiversity and CO₂ Stability (Tobias Stern, University of Graz) 19:00-19:10 Forests provide a wide range of ecosystem services that are crucial not only for the general public but also for forest owners. This presentation highlighted how biodiversity and CO₂ stability are considered essential for the provision of the forest ecosystem services within the Forest EcoValue project. Prof. Tobias Stern explained how different forest management techniques contribute to enhancing forest resilience and stabilizing the carbon cycle.

2. Project Presentation: Forest EcoValue and the Reverse Auction (Tobias Stern, University of Graz) 19:10-19:30

The Interred Alpine Space project “Forest EcoValue” is developing innovative approaches to optimize forest management both ecologically and economically. At its core is the concept of the "Reverse Auction"—a market-like mechanism that provides financial incentives for forest owners to implement sustainable management practices. Tobias Stern explained how this model works, its benefits, and how forest owners could actively participate.

3. Practical Examples from the Perspective of a Small Forest Owner (Alexander Pinter, WoodCluster Styria and Bernd Poinsitt, CEO of Styrian Forest Owners Association) 19:30-19:45

What does sustainable forest management look like in practice? In this session, Alexander Pinter and Bernd Poinsitt shared their first-hand experiences as small forest owners. They presented concrete examples of economically and ecologically viable measures, highlighted challenges, and discussed potential solutions. Topics included the integration of biodiversity conservation with economic use and innovative ways to enhance the value of the forest.

4. Questions and discussion 19:45-20:00

Materials presented: slides

Photos or screenshots:

Media presence:

- Press release: <https://www.holzcluster-steiermark.at/news/neue-geschaeftsmodelle-fuer-waldbesitzerinnen/>
- The event announcement was published on the Styrian Forest Owners Association website: <https://www.waldverband-stmk.at/waldmontage/waldwirtschaft-im-wandel-das-geschaeft-mit-biodiversitaet-und-co2/>
- The event was recorded: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Gwhxfe4BUeg&ab_channel=WaldverbandSteiermark

4.1.3 Feedback Collected

Forest owners asked questions about the details of participation in the Living Lab. Generally, the initiative was appreciated and welcomed by the audience:

- “I think it's great that there could be some compensation for this in the future. I started implementing many of these measures over 30 years ago, and new ones are constantly being added.” (Forest Owner)
- “Thank you very much for this great initiative. Styria is far ahead of Bavaria. We have far too much bureaucracy here.” (Forest Owner)

4.1.4 Outcomes and follow-up

Questions and feedback received during the discussion were integrated into the Living Lab application and supported further promotion of the initiative among forest owners.

4.2 Austrian Living Lab – Final event

4.2.1 Event Details

Final public event in the Austrian Living Lab, organized during the Cluster Forum WoodCluster Styria (Clusterforum Holzcluster Steiermark)

Date: October 8, 2025, 13:00-15:00

Location: WoodCluster Styria, Reininghausstraße 13a, 8020 Graz

Format: At the Cluster Forum, the format was organized as a World Café with three thematic tables. A total of 43 participants rotated in three groups, each spending 40 minutes per table to discuss various future-oriented topics of the wood-based sector. One of the three thematic tables focused on the Forest EcoValue project. The discussions centered on the monetisation of forest ecosystem services, the experiences from the Styrian Living Lab, and the further development of FES payment models. Thanks to the rotating setup, all participants were actively involved in the exchange and were able to contribute their perspectives on the proposed solutions.

Agenda:

1. Welcome & Introduction

2. Presentation of Project Results
3. Discussion: Monetisation of Ecosystem Services
4. Presentation of the Regional Roadmap

Stakeholders involved:

In total, 43 people attended the event, representing the following sectors:

- Forestry (TG4, TG11, TG16)
- Wood industry (TG6, TG10)
- Research (TG17)
- Public administration (TG3, TG5)
- Financial institutions (TG15)

The Final Public Event of Forest EcoValue, held as part of the Cluster Forum of Holzcluster Steiermark on 22 October 2025, brought together a total of 43 participants. Among them were representatives from forestry, industry, research, public administration, and financial institutions. This diverse group enabled an in-depth exchange on the future development of payment models for forest ecosystem services and the continuation of the Styrian Living Lab.

4.2.2 Content Summary

1. Welcome & Introduction

- Opening by Holzcluster Steiermark
- Presentation of the Interreg Alpine Space project Forest EcoValue and its objectives
- Overview of the Styrian Living Lab

2. Presentation of Project Results

- Implementation of forest ecosystem services in the Living Lab:
 - Retention of habitat trees to promote biodiversity
 - Establishment of continuous cover forestry structures (uneven-aged stands, natural regeneration)
- Presentation of additional planned ecosystem services and best-practice examples from other Alpine regions

3. Discussion: Monetisation of Ecosystem Services

- Discussion with representatives from industry, research, and public administration
- Key topics:
 - Fair remuneration for forest owners
 - Transparent valuation principles and simple submission procedures
 - Liability questions and risk pool approaches
 - Role of financial partners (e.g. Raiffeisen Landesbank Steiermark)

4. Presentation of the Regional Roadmap

- Presentation of the Regional Roadmap Styria
- Discussion of future directions for FES payment models

- Integration of ecosystem services into economic and policy decision-making

5. Outlook & Next Steps

- Refinement of ecological parameters
- Development of the verification concept in cooperation with the Waldverband Steiermark
- Preparation of sponsorship partnerships
- Simplification of participation for forest owners

6. Closing & Networking Session

- Joint reflection on the project results
- Open networking among forest owners, industry, and research representatives

Materials presented:

- Regional Roadmap of Styria
- Slides with the results of the Living Lab

Photos or screenshots:

4.2.3 Feedback Collected

Living Lab results and ideas tested in the participatory process were well received by the stakeholders present, who have shown great interest in the potential of replication and scaling up of the pilot test.

4.2.4 Outcomes and follow-up

Nine letters of commitment to support the Roadmap of the Living Lab were collected as a result of the presentation and discussions at the public event.

As part of the follow-up activities, comprehensive publicity measures were implemented: A news article on the Holzcluster Steiermark website, a social media post, and a feature in the Holzcluster newsletter provided information on the key topics and outcomes of the Forest EcoValue Final Event. In addition, a press release was issued to share the Styrian activities and insights from the project with a broader public audience.

4.3 French Living Lab – Intermediate event

4.3.1 Event Details

Title: Technical exchange tour in the field

Location: Très le Mont, 74470 LULLIN

Date: May 24, 2024, 8.30 – 13.30

Format: In person – workshop only upon invitation, organized by ONF/CNPF

Agenda

- Presentation of the meeting objectives by Lauriane Henet (CRPF)
- Presentation of the local context and forest context by Jean Luc Mabboux (ONF). Specific focus on the water management project – LIFE Alpeau
- Presentation of the geological context and watershed functioning by Adrien Jacquier (Head of water unit management in Thonon Agglomeration)
- Presentation of the political context and historical points by Mr Bel (representative - VP of Thonon Agglomeration)
- Discussion among stakeholders and questions

Stakeholders involved (type and number):

Type of stakeholder	Stakeholders contacted for the event	Stakeholders participating in the event
National public authority (TG 1 and 2):		
Regional public authority (TG 3 and 4):		
Local public authority (TG 5):	2	2 (Thonon / Grand Annecy)
Enterprise, except SME (TG 6 and 7):		
SMEs (TG 8 and 9):		
Business support organization (TG 10):	1	1 (ASLGF Moises)
Sectoral agency (TG 11):	3	3 (ONF74 ; ONF DT AURA ; CNPF)
Interest groups including NGOs (TG 12-14):		

General public (TG 13):		
Higher education, research org. (TG 17):	1	
International organization, EEIG (TG 18 – 19):		
Others (TG 16):		
TOTAL number of Stakeholders (sum):	7	6

4.3.2 Content Summary

Key discussion topics

- Forest EcoValue project presentation and updates among stakeholders involved
- Context of the local territorial scheme between private and public forest owners / managers. The landscape is quite complex as private forests, public forests and agricultural land are mixed. Many stakes were identified by stakeholders concerning the forest management issues (forest infrastructure, high cost of exploitation, type of exploitation, variable wood price)
- Results of the Alpeau project – focus on water protection service supported by local forests. This discussion was very interesting for representatives of Grand Annecy – main questions address the water system management in the Moise watershed (how to retribute forest service, how to maintain water quality and quantity, etc.)
- Functioning of the Moise ASL which pay forest owners for specific measures they carry on for protecting water sources

Materials presented: /

Photos or screenshots:

4.3.3 Feedback Collected

CNPF: has historically worked on LIFE Alp'Eau and on the best way to integrate forest management and water management. This approach could be replicated in other territories and the Forest Eco Value project/methodology disseminated.

ONF: has historically worked on LIFE Alp'Eau and on the best way to integrate forest management and water management. This approach could be replicated in other territories and the Forest Eco Value project/methodology disseminated.

Grand Annecy: elected representatives of Greater Annecy. They want to discover new models for integrating ecosystem services. The Greater Annecy living lab focuses on welcoming the public to the forest and forest management.

Thonon agglomeration: elected representatives of Thonon Agglomeration. They are directly involved in the case of the Moises waterbasin, as the financial framework for the LL is decided at the level of the Thonon conurbation. They also represent the political level at which this LL will be run.

ASLGF Moises: directly implements the system of remuneration for the protection of the service provided by the forest on water. They wish to maintain this system because it provides better remuneration for foresters and enables sustainable management.

4.3.4 Outcomes and follow-up

Specific functioning of the Moise watershed could be a good pilot site for sharing good forest practices for preserving water quality in other living lab (type of exploitation, period of exploitation, etc.).

The market model of water protection service was also very appreciated by representatives as a way to pay foresters for protecting water.

Legal scheme proposed in this specific framework could be reproduced in another territory

4.4 French Living Lab – Final event

4.4.1 Event Details

Title: Dissemination seminar of the Forest EcoValue project - Living Lab Partner

Date: Monday, 29 September 2025, 9.30 – 16.30

Format: Almost entirely in person, with only one presentation given remotely due to the person's inability to attend in person

Location: Annecy – Imperial Hotel.

Agenda:

9:00 – 9:30 Welcome

9:30 – 9:45 Introduction

9:45 – 10:45 Round Table: What are the challenges for forest ecosystem services? Speakers: D. Bonthoux, ANCT – E. Dubois, ONF – N. Traub, CNPF – C. Schwoehrer, CEN74 – J.-L. Desbois, PNRMB

11:00 – 11:30 An Economic Perspective: How to enhance the value of ecosystem services? Speakers: J. Abildtrup, Natural Resource Economist

11:30 – 12:00 Forests and Biodiversity: Enhancing the value of ecosystem services. Speakers: M. Rossi, FSC Expert

12:00 – 12:30 ForestEcoValue: Lessons from the evaluation of ecosystem services. Speakers: F. Berger, Forest Protection Specialist

12:30 – 13:30 Buffet Lunch

13:45 – 16:00 Presentation of a dissemination tool for the general public, technical staff, and elected

officials : forest ecosystem services fresco

16:00 Conclusion and Closing

Stakeholders involved (type and number):

Type of stakeholder	Stakeholders contacted for the event	Stakeholders participating in the event
National public authority (TG 1 and 2):	2	1
Regional public authority (TG 3 and 4):	2	2
Local public authority (TG 5):	7	6
Enterprise, except SME (TG 6 and 7):		
SMEs (TG 8 and 9):	2	1
Business support organization (TG 10):	4	3
Sectoral agency (TG 11):	5	4
Interest groups including NGOs (TG 12-14):	4	4
General public (TG 13):		
Higher education, research org. (TG 17):	3	3
International organization, EEIG (TG 18 – 19):	1	1
Others (TG 16):	1	1
TOTAL number of Stakeholders (sum):	31	26

4.4.2 Content Summary

Key discussion topics

This event is devoted to forest ecosystem services (FES) and also marks the conclusion of the Forest EcoValue project. The aim of this seminar is to:

- Present the main results of the Interreg Forest EcoValue project, which aims to recognise and promote forest ecosystem services;
- Promote the dissemination of knowledge on ecosystem services among experts, technicians and local decision-makers in order to create a common culture;
- Reflect on the place of forests in the local economy and the lives of inhabitants through an educational activity.

The seminar has been opened by Greater Annecy. Several scientific presentations and an educational session are planned for the morning and afternoon respectively. The closing remarks were given by the European Relations Department of the AURA region.

Materials presented: slides

- *An Economic Perspective: How to enhance the value of ecosystem services (J. Abildtrup)*
- *Forests and Biodiversity: Enhancing the value of ecosystem services (M. Rossi)*
- *ForestEcoValue: Lessons from the evaluation of ecosystem services (F Berger)*

Photos or screenshots

Political introduction by M. Rollin - Vice-President for Environment and Air Quality for Greater Anney

Round table moderated by Delphine Bonthoux - National Agency for Territorial Cohesion (ANCT)

An economic perspective: how can we promote ecosystem services? Jens Abildtrup, natural resource economist, INRAE

Forest EcoValue: lessons from the assessment of ecosystem services - F. Berger, protection forest specialist

Forests and biodiversity: promoting ecosystem services - Magali Rossi Forest Stewardship Council (online presentation)

Forest ecosystem services fresco

4.4.3 Feedback Collected

Stakeholders

- **Greater Annecy:** Currently, most of the funding for forest management comes from timber sales, which is no longer sufficient. There is therefore a need to re-examine public policy. The territory positions itself as a testing ground that is closely connected to on-the-ground realities and to the local population, while also recognising the importance of disseminating scientific data and integrating climate change considerations.
- **Region AURA:** At present, there is no regional funding mechanism dedicated to forest ecosystem services. At European level, however, the 2021 forestry strategy does take these services into account. Overall, the forestry sector represents around 4 million jobs in Europe.
- **CNPF:** The primary condition for the provision of ecosystem services is ensuring that forests will still exist in the future. This raises key questions about forest renewal in the context of a health crisis: whether and how to plant, or whether not planting may sometimes be appropriate. Forest owners need reassurance, particularly when objectives other than timber production are at stake.
- **ONF:** Income from timber sales currently finances other ecosystem services. In mountainous areas, where timber quality is average and operating costs are high, this economic model is reaching its limits. Climate change, heatwaves and prolonged droughts are likely to exceed the adaptive capacity of trees, potentially leading to forest cover loss and a reduction in forest services. A compensation scheme for natural forestry handicaps could be envisaged, similar to the ICHN (compensatory allowance for natural handicaps) used in agriculture. At present, a cost reference exists through the forestry component of the French assessment of ecosystems and ecosystem services (EFESE), but this remains a largely theoretical approach that still needs to be operationalised.
- **Bauges PNR:** The PNR has been able to set up visitor facilities in the field thanks to its capacity to mobilise funding linked to its status. However, there is clearly no dedicated funding mechanism for visitor-related services. This highlights the need for a coordinated public policy approach on these issues.
- **INRAE:** Satellite data can be used to measure aerial biomass and forest accessibility, but such data must be complemented by field observations. For example, a platform could be envisaged to capitalise on visitor-related data across the entire territory.
- **UFP74:** It is essential to link ecological and economic considerations; harvesting wood does not necessarily imply anti-ecological practices. There is also a need to raise awareness among users of private forests—particularly mushroom pickers—who benefit from private property without necessarily questioning their use.
- **FNE:** Active participation from the population is required, rather than relying solely on communication efforts. This participation should be channelled through intermediary structures and organisations such as NGOs, Sylv'acctes and professional bodies. In addition, quantified assessments of ecosystem services are necessary to convince elected officials and funders, although they should not serve as a direct basis for remuneration.
- **ASTERS:** Discussions are underway on biodiversity certificates, involving the Region, the PNRs and the CENs, in a manner similar to carbon compensation schemes. This raises questions about the allocation for biodiversity and rural amenities, which is currently distributed in proportion to the protected areas within each municipality. As this is an unallocated tax, it prompts reflection on the choices made within territorial projects and on whether a portion of this funding could remain at the territorial level to finance forest-related services.

4.4.4 Outcomes and follow-up

- 1) Sharing financial and technical ways to be prioritised among local and global stakeholders
 - These projects must be built with other European partners. Forestry partners must be actors and drivers.
 - It is important to promote forest-related activities in the future Common Agricultural Policy like :
 - A scheme could be set up to compensate for the natural forestry handicap, similar to the ICHN (compensatory allowance for natural handicaps) set up in agriculture.
 - In addition to the ERDF (FEADER), on the LIFE and Horizon Europe direct management programme funding for 2026, for Interreg projects we remain interested in forests, with the ambition of bringing more money from Europe to the Alps and the desire to allocate more European funds to mountains and forests. Partners hope to have credit lines on mountains and forests.
 - The issue of the tourist tax surcharge must also be examined for Great Annecy.
 - One option could be an additional tax on building permits, which would finance support for the services provided by forests (see financing of ENS).
 - Why not base the reasoning on the costs avoided? And approach the organisations that would have to bear the costs of a deterioration in service (insurers, water managers).
 - Develop approaches to biodiversity certificates, based on the same principle as carbon offsetting.
 - The new allocation for biodiversity and rural amenities is allocated in proportion to the protected areas in the municipality.
- 2) Using the fresco as a tool to raise awareness of forest ecosystem services and disseminate information about the project
 - Raise awareness of the concept of ecosystem services, educate people about forestry issues, and explain the services provided to the general public, local authorities and professionals in the sector. Going further for project leaders (foresters)

Comment financer la gestion des forêts aux enjeux de forte multifonctionnalité ?

Une étude au cas par cas

L'évaluation permet de mettre en lumière les enjeux. La contractualisation nécessite ensuite de comprendre les bénéficiaires et les volontaires pour contribuer. Il s'agit de mettre autour de la table de nombreuses parties prenantes.

Montage de projet innovant

Durée, montants, et actions financées doivent faire l'objet d'un accord qui scelle la valeur du service. Les modalités varient énormément selon la source financière et la nature des actions.

Vers un processus unifié ?

Fort besoin de politiques reconnaissant les difficultés de gestion liées à la multifonctionnalité des forêts (à l'image du Handicap Naturel) et de canaux de financement homogènes à l'échelle territoriale voire nationale ou européenne.

A suivre: livrables du projet Forest EcoValue en 2026

3) Sharing summaries and recommendations for the French living lab :

Agir pour la politique: synthèse et recommandations

FOREST ECOVALUE

Soutenir la fourniture des services écosystémiques forestiers par le développement de nouveaux marchés et chaînes de valeur durables, circulaires et biosourcés

Ce projet est soutenu par l'Union européenne par le biais du programme Interreg Espace alpin : 1 857 054 €

DES FONDAMENTAUX!

- **Les forêts sont des atouts stratégiques**, fournissant des services écosystémiques vitaux, des emplois et des bénéfices environnementaux.
- **Elles sont menacées** par le changement climatique, les maladies, les ravageurs, l'abandon de gestion et les aléas naturels.
- Assurer leur résilience exige une juste valorisation économique des services qu'elles rendent à la société, une gestion adaptée et une coopération public/privé renforcée.
- **La durabilité** repose sur la reconnaissance des services écosystémiques forestiers (SEF), le partage équitable des coûts et la solidarité entre propriétaires et bénéficiaires.
- L'**adaptation** doit promouvoir biodiversité, solutions fondées sur la nature, nouveaux marchés et modernisation des chaînes de valeur, en cohérence avec les stratégies régionales, les politiques nationales, le Green Deal européen et les engagements internationaux.

7 ORIENTATIONS POLITIQUES PRIORITAIRES

1. **Intégrer les services écosystémiques** : combiner les services pour garantir la viabilité économique des forêts, en s'appuyant sur des outils juridiques et de connaissance.
2. **Renforcer la coopération entre propriétaires** : créer des modèles d'organisation et des cadres juridiques pour remédier à la fragmentation foncière.
3. **Cartographier et gérer les services stratégiques** : identifier les services localisés (protection contre les risques rocheux, qualité de l'eau potable...) et ceux à grande échelle (stockage du carbone, régulation climatique, protection contre les inondations...).
4. **Orienter les fonds de compensation** : affecter une part des revenus environnementaux et carbone pour couvrir les contraintes de gestion et soutenir de nouvelles initiatives.
5. **Développer les capacités et la sensibilisation** : former les acteurs tout au long de la chaîne de valeur et établir une plateforme transnationale pour les données, les opportunités et l'engagement citoyen.
6. **Promouvoir l'innovation** : soutenir les nouveaux produits et services forestiers (chimie verte, matériaux durables) via la certification et le label.
7. **Favoriser une planification durable et flexible** : utiliser des outils adaptables (ex. « contrats forestiers », gouvernance participative, gestion intégrée, prise en compte des incertitudes liées au changement climatique...) pour renforcer la coopération entre les parties prenantes, intégrer les politiques et sécuriser les co-financements.

EN CONCLUSION

Pour des forêts durables et résilientes, il faut :

- Une **compensation financière équitable**
- De la **coopération et solidarité** entre les parties prenantes
- De l'**innovation** dans la **promotion des Services Ecosystémiques Forestiers**, ainsi que dans les **marchés économiques**.

4.5 German Living Lab – Intermediate event

4.5.1 Event Details

Title: “Forest EcoValue - Neue Geschäftsfelder für Waldökosystemleistungen” (Engl: Forest EcoValue – New fields of business for Forest Ecosystem Services)

Date: 26. September 2025, 7.30-9.15 pm

Format: Online information event for forest owners

Agenda:

- 7:30 p.m. Welcome and introduction by Ifuplan
- 7:35 p.m. Presentation of the Forest EcoValue project (Contents and objectives of the project)
- 7:45 p.m. Forest ecosystem services (What are forest ecosystem services, biophysical assessment of forest ecosystem services, good practices for ecosystem services)
- 8:00 p.m. Economic evaluation (Approaches to the economic evaluation of forest ecosystem services)
- 8:15 p.m. Practical examples from the Living Lab (Business models from the German Living Lab and examples of the other Living Labs)
- 8:30 p.m. Conclusion, discussion and questions

Stakeholders involved (type and number):

Type of stakeholder	Stakeholders contacted for the event	Stakeholders participating in the event
National public authority (TG 1 and 2):	4	1
Regional public authority (TG 3 and 4):	3	
Local public authority (TG 5):		
Enterprise, except SME (TG 6 and 7):	1	
SMEs (TG 8 and 9):		
Business support organization (TG 10):		
Sectoral agency (TG 11):	4	
Interest groups including NGOs (TG 12-14):	14	1 forester
General public (TG 13):		
Higher education, research org. (TG 17):	4	
International organization, EEIG (TG 18 – 19):		
Others (TG 16):	2300 forest owners	18 forest owners
TOTAL number of Stakeholders (sum):	2330	19

4.5.2 Content Summary

Key discussion topics

- **Project Framework “Forest EcoValue**
 - **Topic:** The meeting began with a standard introduction to the Interreg project "Forest EcoValue." This included its objectives, partners, funding, and work packages.
 - **Viewpoint:** The project's core objective is to identify and develop new revenue streams for forest owners based on the non-timber values their forests provide. A key methodological component is the use of a Living Lab to test these concepts in a practical setting.
- **Defining and Valuing Forest Ecosystem Services (FES)**
 - **Topic:** The presentation covered the definition of FES and moved into their ecological and economic valuation. We explained the biophysical assessment and mapping of FES on the examples “recreation” and “habitat provision”.
 - **Viewpoint:** When the audience was asked to name FES, the responses were limited to the most obvious ones: **recreation, timber, and carbon sequestration.**
- **New Business Models & Stakeholder Engagement**
 - **Topic:** Two practical business models were presented: "**Burial Forests**" and a "**Green Initiative.**"
 - **Viewpoint:** The presenter, L. B., made a crucial point: public knowledge about forests is low, leading to conflict. By actively engaging stakeholders (e.g., through an artist trail, school cooperations), forest owners can create value and reduce management friction. This is a form of "social FES management."
- **Discussion, Q&A-Session**
 - **Topic:** The Q&A session was the most revealing part of the event, focusing on the attitudes of forest owners and the effectiveness of current incentive programs.

○ **Viewpoint and Opinions:**

- **Inadequate Compensation:** There was a strong consensus that existing financial rewards for FES are insufficient. This is especially true for forests in difficult terrain (e.g., mountain forests), which have high operational costs but provide a high level of public services (e.g., protection from erosion, water regulation).
- **Owner Ideology:** A major barrier to adopting new management practices is the owner's mindset. Many small, conservative owners view their forest as a "savings account" and are resistant to change or outside influence. Financial incentives are seen as the most effective (and sometimes only) way to convince them. However, there are also forest owners who are genuinely committed to sustainable forest management and proactively engage in it. These are often the same owners who actively seek out and utilize available financial incentives and funding opportunities.
- **Lack of demand:** Forest ecosystem services have received less attention to date. The WBV is more concerned with supporting forest owners in their forest management activities. As an association that is there for its members, the WBV is open to all ideas. However, there have been no specific requests from forest owners to date.

Materials presented

- Power point presentation
- Speech of forest owner L.B. for Business Model “Green Initiative”

Photos or screenshots

Agenda

19:30 Uhr	Begrüßung und Einführung Begrüßung durch die Firma ifuplan
19:35 Uhr	Vorstellung des Projekts Forest EcoValue Inhalte und Ziele des Projekts
19:45 Uhr	Waldökosystemleistungen Was sind Waldökosystemleistungen? Methoden zur Darstellung von Waldökosystemleistungen
20:00 Uhr	Ökonomische Bewertung Ansätze zur ökonomischen Bewertung von Waldökosystemleistungen
20:15 Uhr	Praxisbeispiele aus dem Reallabor Praxisbeispiele aus dem Alpenraum
20:30 Uhr	Abschluss und Fragen Ausblick und Beantwortung von Fragen

Media presence:

- Newsletter “FEV_newsletter_2025-09” to announce the intermediate event
- ifuplan homepage: <https://www.ifuplan.de/neue-einblicke-in-unser-projekt-forest-ecovalue-zusammenfassung-der-info-veranstaltung-am-26-09-2025/>
- LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ifuplan_ifuplan-aktuelles-blog-activity-7380915872044969985--gHf?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAEBelxIB5GaU4A_CzCs1UQ0EMAKKLSsUo8I

4.5.3 Feedback Collected

The discussion was mainly about:

- Inadequate compensation for Forest Ecosystem Services
- Forest Owner’s ideology and possibilities for financial incentives
- Lack of demand for monetizing forest ecosystem services which maybe is because of a lack of knowledge about the importance of the forest and its ecosystem services

After the Intermediate Event one feedback has been collected from the forest owners association Holzkirchen (WBV Holzkirchen) based on the Satisfactory survey. The feedback is summarized in the D.2.1.1., chapter “1.3.3. Germany”

Otherwise, the audience, which consisted mainly of forest owners, was rather reserved.

4.5.4 Outcomes and follow-up

Conclusion/Results from the discussion: it is necessary to adequately reward forest ecosystem services financially. In order to motivate even skeptical forest owners to change their forest management practices, attractive financial incentives must be created.

4.6 German Living Lab – Final event

4.6.1 Event Details

The final event took place during the Forest Science Conference which, organised by the University of Freiburg, was conducted in person as part of the national forestry conference, providing a platform to present and discuss the results of the Forest EcoValue project with experts, researchers, and forest stakeholders from across Germany.

Location: Freiburg im Breisgau, Forest Science Conference 2025

Date: the event took place from 29.09.2025 to 01.10.2025. The German LL participated on the dates **30.09** with a power point presentation and **01.10** with a poster presentation.

Format: Open public event in-person

- Title of power point presentation: Forest EcoValue – transnational experiences from forest ecosystem services to business models

- Title of poster: Forest EcoValue. Reallabor mit Privatwaldbesitzern. Entwicklungsraum für Geschäftsmodelle zur Förderung von Waldökosystemleistungen (Eng: Forest EcoValue. Living Lab with Forest Owners. Development space for business models promoting forest ecosystem services)

Agenda for Power point presentation and the poster presentation:

- Presentation of the Forest EcoValue project: background, contents, objectives of the project
- Forest ecosystem services: brief explanation, methods for indication
- Economic evaluation: Approaches for forest ecosystem services
- Business model examples from the Living Lab and partner LLs
- Conclusion, discussion and questions

Stakeholders involved (type and number)

It was noted that detailed numbers for the different stakeholder groups were not available, as the event had not been organised by the project team and the professional background of participants attending the presentation and poster session was therefore unknown.

Type of stakeholder	Stakeholders contacted for the event	Stakeholders participating in the event
National public authority (TG 1 and 2):		x
Regional public authority (TG 3 and 4):		x
Local public authority (TG 5):		x
Enterprise, except SME (TG 6 and 7):		
SMEs (TG 8 and 9):		
Business support organization (TG 10):		
Sectoral agency (TG 11):		x
Interest groups including NGOs (TG 12-14):		
General public (TG 13):		
Higher education, research org. (TG 17):		x
International organization, EEIG (TG 18 – 19):		
Others (TG 16):		x
TOTAL number of Stakeholders (sum):	Over 600 conference participants	Presentation: about 50; Poster: about 20

Out of the total number of stakeholders who participated, the exact number of key stakeholders is unknown. However, the majority appeared to come from the following groups: TG 1&2, TG 3&4, TG 5, TG 11, TG 16, and TG 17.

4.6.2 Content Summary

Key discussion topics

- Power point presentation: Methodology of ForestEcoValue, introduction of selected forest ecosystem services, economic valuation, business models and presentation of challenges, feasibility and opportunities as transnational observations
- Poster presentation: Details on how FES can be quantified, on the actual business ideas in German LL and the partners LL as well as new potential ideas

Materials presented

- Power point presentation
- Poster presentation

Photos or screenshots

Forest EcoValue

Reallabor mit Privatwaldbesitzern

Entwicklungsraum für Geschäftsmodelle zur Förderung von Waldökosystemleistungen

Autoren: Stefan Marzelli, Andrea Emmer, Thomas Dichtl, Hieronymus Jäger
 ifuplan Institut für Umweltplanung und Raumentwicklung GmbH & Co. KG

Waldökosysteme als Wirtschaftsmodell

Ziel ist es, nachhaltige Geschäftsmodelle für Waldökosystemleistungen zu entwickeln. Dadurch soll die Produktionskraft alpiner Wälder geschützt und gefördert werden. Durch innovative Anreizsysteme möchten wir Waldbesitzern neue Möglichkeiten eröffnen, Wertschöpfung jenseits der traditionellen Holzlieferkette zu erzielen und gleichzeitig einen Beitrag zu einer klimaresilienten Waldbewirtschaftung leisten.

Was ist ein Reallabor?

- ✓ Wissenschaft und Praxis zusammenzubringen, um gemeinsam neue Ideen und Wertschöpfungsketten zu entwickeln und zu erproben.
- ✓ Durch transdisziplinäre Dialoge sollen die Beteiligten voneinander lernen und ein Transformationsprozess angestoßen werden.

Das deutsche Reallabor im Bayerischen Voralpenland

1. Entdecken

Inhalte

- Bestandserfassung
- Ökologische Bewertung
- Kartenerstellung

Indikator-Karten

- Interessen und Wünsche der Beteiligten
- Sammlung von guten Praxisbeispielen

Factsheets

- Kick-off-Treffen
- Stakeholder-Analyse
- Auswahl relevanter ÖSL

Ziele

Information & Bewusstmachung

2. Umsetzungsplanung

Inhalte

- Vor-Ort-Begänge der Waldflächen mit den Besitzern → Validierung der ökologischen Bewertung

- Auswertung der Waldbesitzerinteressen

- Auswahl von Geschäftsideen

Ziele

Konzeptentwicklung

3. Umsetzung

Inhalte

- Machbarkeitsabschätzung der Geschäftsmodelle
- Gemeinsames Prüfen und Konkretisierung der Geschäftsmodelle

Bestattungswald

ÖSL: Erholungsraum, spirituelle Geschäftsmodelle: Alternative zu klass. Beerdigung, Eigenbedarf od. Verpachtung, Rahmenbedingungen: 5-10 ha Wald, gutes Wegenetz u. Verkehrsanbindung, abwechslungsreiches Waldbild, Waldbewirtschaft. eingeschrieben

Grüne Initiative

ÖSL: Erholungsleistung, Teilzeiter Waldkirchen Geschäftsmodelle: Plattform die Naturpädagogik, Kunst, Kultur und Naturschutz verbindet. Honorarverursacher: Fördergelder, Mitgliedsbeiträge, Kooperation, Beteiligung an Kurtaxe

Ziele

Szenarien für die Umsetzung

4. Bewertung

Inhalte

- Ökonomische Bewertung der Geschäftsmodelle durch Projektpartner
- Politikempfehlungen & Lernangebote

Ausblick:

- Winterschool im Dezember
- Capacity Building Workshops

Ziele

Reflexion & Bewertung der Machbarkeit

Reallabore der Projektpartner im Interreg-Alpenraum

- Italien:** Vermarktung von Nicht-Holzprodukten zur Förderung der Waldbewirtschaftung
- Frankreich:** Finanzielle Förderung von Waldökosystemleistungen durch eine Kurtaxe
- Slowenien:** Finanzielle Förderung für die Schutzwirkung des Waldes
- Österreich:** "Reverse Auction" von Waldökosystemleistungen

Media presence:

- Newsletter “**FEV_newsletter_2025-09**” to announce the intermediate event
- Ifuplan-Homepage: <https://www.ifuplan.de/final-public-event-des-projekts-forest-ecovalue-auf-der-forstwissenschaftlichen-tagung-2025-in-freiburg/>
- LinkedIn (announcement of Event): https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ifuplan_herbst-veranstaltungen-activity-7384952205700931584-bKqv?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAAEEBSYUBakLlOqAMeT9Bj8yc-tLgpEIC7Aw

4.6.3 Feedback Collected

In general, there has been positive feedback from several people about the FEV project, especially on the developed business models.

Interesting feedback and comments after Poster presentation:

- One person from Bavarian State Institute for Forestry and Forest Management (LWF) working on the CarboKlimPlus project found the topic of ecosystem services and their remuneration interesting.
- One person of the project “Small4Goods” was very interested in the business models and the structure of forest owners in the living labs
- Another person, a 5G sensor developer, was interested in business models too and believes that the sensors he is developing offer the possibility of quantifying ecosystem services (e.g. water provision).

4.6.4 Outcomes and follow-up

- No specific external outcomes or follow-up were recorded.

- The project partners internally concluded that the assessment and remuneration of ecosystem services represent a highly relevant and widely debated topic, as evidenced by the numerous contributions presented at the Forestry Science Conference on ecosystem services, including those related to Living Lab approaches.

4.7 Italian Living Lab – Intermediate event

4.7.1 Event Details

Event: Presentation of the Final Business Model and Regional Roadmap – Valle Tanaro Living Lab

Date: 5 September 2025

Location: Municipality of Ormea

Format: In-person meeting, frontal presentations and open discussion

Duration: Approximately 2.5 hours

Agenda:

- Results from the biophysical assessment and territorial analysis
- Presentation of the final Business Model developed for the Valle Tanaro Living Lab
- Presentation of the Regional Roadmap and implementation strategy
- Final discussion led by the *Regione Piemonte – Sustainable Development and Climate Change Department*, focusing on next steps and potential financial instruments to support implementation

Stakeholders Involved:

Based on the attendance sheet and minutes, eight key stakeholders participated, representing different categories:

- **Regional public authority:** Regione Piemonte – Sustainable Development and Climate Change Department
- **Local public authorities:** Municipality of Ormea and Municipality of Ceva
- **Forest and land management entities:** Monte Armetta Forest Consortium, Ormea Landowner Association (ASFO)
- **Enterprises and cooperatives:** Cooperative *La Volpe e il Mirtillo*
- **Educational and research bodies:** ISS Baruffi – Forestry School of Ormea
- **Civil society and NGOs:** Gruppo Micologico Cebano

In total, 73 stakeholders had been previously contacted for participation, confirming the broad representativeness of the Living Lab network.

Type of stakeholder	Stakeholders contacted for the event	Stakeholders participating in the event
National public authority (TG 1 and 2):	0	0
Regional public authority (TG 3 and 4):	4	1
Local public authority (TG 5):	25	2
Enterprise, except SME (TG 6 and 7):	3	0
SMEs (TG 8 and 9):	16	1
Business support organization (TG 10):	4	0
Sectoral agency (TG 11):	0	0
Interest groups including NGOs (TG 12-14):	7	2
General public (TG 13):	9	1
Higher education, research org. (TG 17):	5	1
International organization, EEIG (TG 18 – 19):	0	0
Others (TG 16):		
TOTAL number of Stakeholders (sum):	73	8

4.7.2 Content Summary

Key Discussion Topics:

The meeting served as the official presentation of the *final Business Model and Roadmap* for the Valle Tanaro Living Lab, concluding the feasibility and co-design phase.

Main themes included:

- **Results of the biophysical and economic analysis** of the territory, highlighting the multifunctional potential of the local forest ecosystem.
- **Structure and feasibility of the integrated Business Model**, combining forest restoration, carbon and biodiversity crediting, and value chains for timber, non-wood forest products, and tourism.
- **Implementation pathways**, including the activation of public–private partnerships and blended finance mechanisms to sustain the model.
- **Connection with public instruments**, with a specific focus on possible integration within *Regional Rural Development Programmes (CSR 2023–2027)*, *Green Communities*, and compensatory measures linked to quarry exploitation concessions.
- **Governance and local alliances**, emphasising the role of ASFOs, consortia, municipalities, and cooperatives in the territorial roadmap.

Materials Presented:

PowerPoint presentations were delivered by:

- *Finpiemonte* (Susanna Longo) – project coordination and framework introduction
- *IPLA* (Paolo Camerano) – technical feasibility and ecological impacts
- *Walden srl* (Lucio Vaira) – business model structure and roadmap

The visual materials summarised the methodological process, financial modelling results, implementation matrix, and potential impacts in terms of carbon sequestration, biodiversity

improvement, and local employment.

Photos or screenshots:

Photos were taken during the presentations and discussion sessions inside the Ormea Town Hall, showing the participation of regional and local representatives, and the final plenary brainstorming activity.

Media presence:

- <https://www.finpiemonte.it/news/incontro-di-chiusura-del-progetto-pilota-forest-ecoalue>
- <https://www.finpiemonte.it/news/forest-ecoalue-la-valle-tanaro-laboratorio-di-innovazione-forestale>

4.7.3 Feedback Collected

Feedback was gathered through satisfaction surveys distributed at the end of the event. Key results can be summarised as follows:

- Overall satisfaction: Participants expressed a good level of appreciation for both the event and the participatory process leading to it.
- Clarity and relevance: Presentations were judged clear, informative, and well-structured, allowing participants to understand the final outputs of the Living Lab and their practical implications.
- Engagement and facilitation: The final discussion facilitated by the regional authority was perceived as particularly useful, providing a concrete link between local needs and regional policy frameworks.
- Future involvement: Several participants indicated their willingness to remain involved in future phases or pilot projects, confirming a sense of shared ownership.

4.7.4 Outcomes and follow-up

The intermediate restitution event marked a key transition from the design to the implementation phase of the Italian Living Lab.

Main outcomes:

- Formal presentation and validation of the final Business Model and Roadmap, shared and endorsed by local and regional stakeholders.
- Collection of new expressions of interest from actors willing to collaborate in the forthcoming implementation phase, including:
Gruppo Micologico Cebano, Comune di Ormea, Finpiemonte, Cooperativa La Volpe e il Mirtillo, Walden srl, ASFO Pamparà, Consorzio Forestale Monte Armetta, and the Scuola Forestale di Ormea.
- Institutional alignment with the *Regione Piemonte – Sustainable Development and Climate Change Department*, which acknowledged the Living Lab results and facilitated a policy-oriented discussion on potential financial tools (CSR silvo-climatic payments, PES schemes, Green Communities).
- Strategic convergence on the need to activate pilot actions under a “territorial pact” among municipalities, consortia, and local enterprises to test the integrated business model.

The event therefore succeeded in consolidating multi-level cooperation between local and regional actors, providing a robust foundation for the final implementation stage of the Valle Tanaro Roadmap.

4.8 Italian Living Lab – Final event

4.8.1 Event Details

Event: Italian Living Lab – Final restitution and dissemination webinar

Date: 27 November 2025

Location: Online (Webex platform)

Format: Webinar at national scale, open to partners and stakeholders across the Alpine region

Duration: Approximately 2 hours

Statement on the Delay: *The event, originally planned for early autumn, was postponed to late November 2025 in order to allow sufficient time for the completion of data collection and the preparation of presentations reflecting the work carried out across all Living Labs. This adjustment ensures a more comprehensive and representative restitution, aligning the Italian event with the overall project timeline and guaranteeing the quality and consistency of the final results presented.*

Agenda:

- Opening remarks – Finpiemonte (10 min): Institutional introduction and overview of the Italian Living Lab process.
- WP2 and Business Model archetypes – Luca Cetara (15–30 min): Comparative presentation of the methodological framework and synthesis of business model types emerging across Living Labs.
- Presentations from other Living Labs (30–40 min): Short insights on the models developed in France, Austria, Germany, and Slovenia.
- Italian Living Lab presentation – Lucio Vaira, Walden srl (20 min): Final restitution of the Valle Tanaro Living Lab outcomes, including business model validation and roadmap

implementation strategies.

- Concluding remarks – Finpiemonte: Reflections and next steps for regional and transnational capitalisation.

Stakeholders involved (type and number):

The final webinar will target an extended audience beyond the Valle Tanaro area, including regional and national stakeholders. Approximately **40 participants** are expected, representing:

- Regional and national public authorities (Piemonte Region – Sustainable Development and Climate Change Dept., Rural Development Dept.)
- Project partners and representatives of other FEV Living Labs
- Universities and research institutes (e.g., FLA, IPLA, University of Turin)
- Professional associations (Order of Agronomists and Foresters – accreditation requested)
- Enterprises, cooperatives, and forest consortia involved in the Italian LL
- NGOs and civil society organisations active in forest, biodiversity and climate topics

Type of stakeholder	Stakeholders contacted for the event	Stakeholders participating in the event
National public authority (TG 1 and 2):	1	
Regional public authority (TG 3 and 4):	22	5
Local public authority (TG 5):	43	1
Enterprise, except SME (TG 6 and 7):	6	1
SMEs (TG 8 and 9):	58	4
Business support organization (TG 10):	10	2
Sectoral agency (TG 11):		1
Interest groups including NGOs (TG 12-14):	18	4
General public (TG 13):	30	
Higher education, research org. (TG 17):	13	5
International organization, EEIG (TG 18 – 19):		
Others (TG 16):		
TOTAL number of Stakeholders (sum):	201	26

4.8.2 Content Summary

Key discussion topics:

This final event was held with a slight delay compared to the initial schedule, as it was originally planned for October.

This final event represents the closing milestone of the Italian Living Lab process and aims to disseminate results at a wider level, sharing the outcomes achieved and situating them within the broader framework of the FEV transnational pilot action.

In fact, the Living Lab Coordinator considered it preferable to dedicate the intermediate event (5 September 2025) to a moment of restitution towards local stakeholders, aimed at validating and

approving the Regional Roadmap, and instead to organise the final event with broader scope and visibility, involving a wider audience of actors potentially interested in the topic and in the outcomes developed within the FEV pilot action.

For this reason, it was deemed appropriate to allow sufficient time to pass after the intermediate event (and after the second Capacity Building Workshop, which also took place in September), before holding the final event.

Main discussion areas will include:

- Overview of WP2 synthesis and Business Model archetypes, highlighting common features and differences among the Alpine Living Labs.
- Final presentation of the Valle Tanaro Business Model and Roadmap, focusing on feasibility results, governance structure, and identified financial mechanisms.
- Cross-comparison with other national and European Living Labs, with emphasis on replicability and lessons learned.
- Opportunities for policy uptake through regional instruments such as the *Complemento di Sviluppo Rurale 2023–2027*, *Green Communities*, and climate-biodiversity payment schemes.
- Scaling perspectives and future collaboration, including potential alignment with ongoing LIFE, Interreg, and NBFC initiatives coordinated in Piedmont.

Materials presented:

All presentations will be delivered in Italian and collected in a single digital report for dissemination. The webinar will include PowerPoint presentations prepared by Finpiemonte, FLA, and Walden, and will follow a plenary format with a final Q&A and open discussion among speakers and participants to encourage exchange on transferability, policy recommendations, and future collaboration opportunities.

Photo or screenshots:

4.8.3 Feedback collected

The final restitution webinar generated a good level of interest among participants, who appreciated the opportunity to access a consolidated overview of project activities regarding business modelling and transnational Living Labs experiences, with a broader transnational perspective. Compared to more locally focused events, active interventions from the audience were more limited, reflecting the wider and more heterogeneous profile of participants and the primarily dissemination-oriented format of the event. Nevertheless, feedback highlighted the clarity of the presentations, the usefulness of the comparative insights across Living Labs, and the relevance of the Italian case study as a concrete example of integrated forest ecosystem service valorisation. Overall, the event was perceived as coherent, informative, and valuable for professional, academic and policy-oriented audiences.

4.8.4 Outcomes and follow-up

One of the main outcomes of the event was the strengthening of networking opportunities at supralocal and national level, enabling connections between project partners, regional institutions, researchers, and practitioners beyond the Valle Tanaro context. The webinar facilitated the collection of new contacts, laying the groundwork for potential future collaborations, knowledge exchange, and follow-up initiatives. In addition, the event contributed to increasing the visibility of project and Living Lab results and to positioning them within ongoing policy and research debates on forest ecosystem services, blended finance, and climate- and biodiversity-smart forestry. As follow-up actions, the collected contacts and insights will support further dissemination activities, potential pilot initiatives, and the integration of Living Lab outcomes into future projects, funding opportunities, and regional or transnational cooperation frameworks.

4.9 Slovenian Living Lab – Intermediate event

4.9.1 Event Details

Title: “Presentation of the project Forest EcoValue and recreation and tourism in Municipality Tržič”

Date: May 28 2025, 18.00 - 20.00

Location: Tržič, business incubator Tržič

Format: In person

Agenda:

- Presentation of the project and main activities in the municipality
- Presentation of recreation and tourism (activities, results of the survey about recreation and tourism in the municipality)

Stakeholders involved (type and number)

The event was promoted through municipal channels and via email.

Type of stakeholder	Stakeholders participating in the event
National public authority (TG 1 and 2):	Slovenia Forest Service – forest and game planning departments: 3
Regional public authority (TG 3 and 4):	
Local public authority (TG 5):	Municipality of Tržič: 1
Enterprise, except SME (TG 6 and 7):	
SMEs (TG 8 and 9):	Mountain guides: 1, “Natura Slovenika” (mushroom club): 1, “Soul Bike” club: 1
Business support organization (TG 10):	BSC regional development agency: 1
Sectoral agency (TG 11):	
Interest groups including NGOs (TG 12-14):	Mountaineering clubs: 1, (“Natura Slovenika” 1, “Soul Bike” club 1 could be in this group as well)
General public (TG 13):	
Higher education, research org. (TG 17):	
International organization, EEIG (TG 18 – 19):	
Others (TG 16):	Forest owners: 1
TOTAL number of Stakeholders (sum):	10

4.9.2 Content Summary

Key discussion topics

- Project and project’s main activities in the LL
- Recreation and tourism in forest areas
- Recreation and tourism in LL (activities, results of the survey in the municipality)
- Discussion among participants

Materials presented: PPT presentation

Photos or screenshots

4.9.3 Feedback Collected

Despite promotion of the event through local media and mailing lists, attendance was relatively low. Within a short period, several workshops were organized in the area, which likely led to a certain level of public saturation with similar events. Moreover, workshops or events that are more thematically focused and tailored to specific target groups tend to attract higher participation, while broadly oriented events generally receive less attention. Nevertheless, the event was considered successful. Participants learned new information, and the meeting provided an opportunity for their interests and concerns to be heard. The atmosphere was relaxed, and the discussion was engaging. Attendees shared their worries and proposals. For example, there was a discussion about tourists camping in the Jelendol area and questions regarding who should be contacted in such cases. It was clarified that if tourists are staying on municipal land (e.g., next to the kindergarten), the municipality can be contacted; otherwise, the relevant inspection service is responsible. Another noteworthy suggestion concerned driving in forest areas. It was mentioned that in each LL hunting inspection authorities impose higher penalties, and their involvement could be an effective way to ensure greater compliance with driving restrictions.

4.9.4 Outcomes and follow-up

To achieve higher attendance, it is important to focus on concrete and well-defined topics. It is also recommended to avoid scheduling too many events within a short timeframe, as this may diminish public interest and participation.

4.10 Slovenian Living Lab – Final event

4.10.1 Event Details

Title: “Final event of the project Forest EcoValue”

Date: November 26 2025, 14:00. - 18:00

Explanation of the delay: *The organisation of the event was postponed due to the high number of commitments, deadlines, and public activities involving key stakeholders at the beginning of autumn. In order to ensure a high-quality event with strong participation, the intention was to identify a date that would allow the broadest possible attendance, particularly from those stakeholders most closely involved throughout the project and whose engagement remains essential for the continued development of ecosystem services and related opportunities.*

Location: Tržič, business incubator Tržič

Format: In person

Agenda

- Introductory greeting by the organizer and the mayor
- Presentation of the main project goals, activities, and results
- Round table with six panelists on the FES themes addressed in the Living Lab: biomass, torrent management, recreation, and tourism
- Open debate

Stakeholders involved (type and number)

116 stakeholders have been contacted and invited via email.

Type of stakeholder	Stakeholders contacted for the event	Stakeholders participating in the event
National public authority (TG 1 and 2):	Water agency Slovenia, Institute of the Republic of Slovenia for Nature Conservation, Civil Protection Tržič, Fire department Tržič, Slovenia Forest Service, Triglav National Park, Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food, Geological survey of Slovenia,	Slovenia Forest Service: 7 Triglav National Park: 1 Geological survey of Slovenia: 1
Regional public authority (TG 3 and 4):		
Local public authority (TG 5):	Municipalities Tržič, Jesenice, Naklo, Jezersko, Radovljica, Preddvor, Jezersko, Kranj	Municipality Tržič: 4; Municipality Naklo: 1
Enterprise, except SME (TG 6 and 7):	Companies dealing with harvesting and biomass Gajles d.o.o., MEGALES d.o.o, SIDG d.o.o. - Slovenian state forests, Utility company (Komunala Kočevje), Hidrotehnik d.o.o., water consionare, Local newspapers Gorenjski glas, Tržičan, Local radio Gorenc, Tourism information center (TIC) Tržič,	Utility company (Komunala Kočevje – best practice example): 1; MEGALES d.o.o.: 1
SMEs (TG 8 and 9):	Touristic farms	Touristic farms: 1
Business support organization (TG 10):	Development agencies SORA, RAGOR, BSC Kranj	Development agency RAGOR: 1
Sectoral agency (TG 11):	Local Energy Agency of Gorenjska LEAG	
Interest groups including NGOs (TG 12-14):	Forest owner association, Forest owners association of Gorenjska, Mountaineering clubs Križe, Šija, Tržič, "Natura Slovenika" mushroom club, "Soulbikes" bike club, Mountain, Rescue service Tržič	Mountaineering clubs Križe, Šija: 2
General public (TG 13):		
Higher education, research org. (TG 17):	Forest institute Slovenia, Biotechnical faculty, Department for Forestry	Biotechnical faculty, Department for Forestry: 1
International organization, EEIG (TG 18 – 19):	EUSALP AG7	
Others (TG 16):	Forest owners (those who participated at our events in the past)	Representative of forest owners: 1 International PhD student: 1
TOTAL number of Stakeholders (sum):	116	24

4.10.2 Content Summary

Key discussion topics

The event began with welcoming remarks from the organizer and the mayor, setting the stage for presentations on the project's key achievements. The programme highlighted the importance of FES for local communities, outlining the project's major goals, activities, and results across three core areas: sustainable biomass use, innovative torrent management solutions, and new approaches to recreation and tourism. These insights then fed into a round-table discussion moderated by a facilitator and joined

by six experts, who further explored the implications of the findings and their potential to support future regional development.

The debate was very successful, featuring numerous examples of good practices, ideas for further development of FES, and in-depth expertise. It also offered a fresh and engaging perspective on the project's work. Thanks to the format of the event, stakeholder participation was particularly effective and dynamic.

Photos or screenshots:

